

Multiscale analysis of particulate nanocomposites-thermomechanical properties

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SUMMARY

In this study, thermomechanical properties of epoxy-based nanocomposites including different sized alumina(Al_2O_3) nanoparticles are investigated using molecular dynamics(MD) simulations. The sequential multi-scale analysis considering the size effects of nanoparticles is proposed by transferring the information of MD simulation results to the continuum model

Keywords: Multiscale simulation, micromechanics, molecular dynamics, thermomechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Polymer-based nanocomposites have wide applications such as NEMS/MEMS device, electronic packaging, aeronautical structures and so on. In these applications, efficient reinforcing effects are needed in order to achieve adequate mechanical and thermal properties of structures such as elastic modulus, coefficient of thermal expansion(CTE) and glass transition temperature(T_g). In nano-sized materials, the ratio of the surface to volume increases remarkably as compared with micro and macro size materials. The multi-functionality of nanocomposites is very sensitive to the size of nano-fillers. It was reported that the CTE of PEEK matrix composites was reduced to 60% compared to pure PEEK at 43 vol% micro- Al_2O_3 and at 12 vol% nano- Al_2O_3 by Goyal et al[1]. Cho et al. measured the elastic modulus of vinyl ester composites with nano- Al_2O_3 (15nm) and compared it to modulus of composite with macro Al_2O_3 (0.5mm)[2]. The larger values were estimated in the composites including nano-particles. So the size effect of the nano-filler on the thermomechanical properties has been investigated widely and actively using Molecular dynamics (MD) simulation method[3,4].

MD simulation can describe the atomistic structures and behaviours but needs too much computing time and resources. Because the method has limitations for the design of composites or large scale problems, multi-scale analysis based on the micromechanics model has been developed[5]. But a conventional micromechanics model does not describe the size effects of particles. Therefore the bridging method based on MD simulation results has been developed for reflecting the size effects[6].

In this study, thermomechanical properties of nanocomposites of thermoset polymer epoxy, composed of EPON862[®] and TETA[®], is investigated for the various size of

alumina nanoparticles through MD simulations. Using the MD simulations results, multi-scale bridging method was developed.

SIMULATION MODEL

Materials

The nanocomposites unit cell is constructed with epoxy resin and alumina nanoparticles. The epoxy resin considered the cross-linking structures is composed of EPON862[®] as the epoxy and TETA[®] as the curing agent. The cross-linking bond is generated between the curing sites of each materials, the epoxide group in EPON862[®] and the nitrogen groups(NH, NH₃) in TETA[®]. The molecular reaction ratio is three molecules of EPON862[®] to one molecules of TETA[®] and the ratio is based on the weight ratio (100:15.4). Based on this cross-linking ration, the representative cross-linked epoxy unit consists of three molecules of EPON862[®] and one molecule of TETA[®] as shown in Figure 1. As the reinforcing filler of the nanocomposites, spherical alumina particle which have no surface functionalization or direct bonding with epoxy molecules at the surface is used.

Fig. 1 The composition of nanocomposites unit cell

Table 1 Compositions of Epoxy/alumina nanocomposites unit-cells

	Particle Radius[Å]	No. of EPON862 [®]	No. of TETA [®]	Cell Length [Å]	Volume Fraction
CASE 1	6.0	27	9	25.34	
CASE 2	7.0	45	15	29.64	
CASE 3	7.9	63	21	33.47	
CASE 4	8.2	72	24	34.80	0.055
CASE 5	8.6	81	27	36.38	
CASE 6	8.9	90	30	37.70	
CASE 7	10.0	126	42	42.30	

Unit cell compositions

In order to investigate the size effects of particles in mechanical and thermal properties, totally seven unit cells are constructed. The radius of the nanoparticle included in the cells varies from 6~10Å. To restrict other influences except the size effect of particles, the cell construction conditions such as the volume fraction of the alumina particles and the density of the unit cells are fixed. The volume fraction of filler is set at 5.5 vol% and the density of the unit cell is defined 1.23g/cm³. The details of the cell compositions are arranged in Table 1.

MD SIMULATION METHOD

Force Field

In order to construct the initial molecular structures and implement all ensemble simulations and post processes, a commercial molecular simulation program Material Studio® 4.2 [7] has been used, and *ab initio* COMPASS(Condensed-phase Optimized Molecular Potentials for Atomistic Simulation Studies) force field was applied to describe inter- and intra-atomic interactions, as the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{total} = & \sum_b \left[K_2 (b - b_o)^2 + K_3 (b - b_o)^3 + K_4 (b - b_o)^4 \right] + \sum_{\theta} \left[H_2 (\theta - \theta_o)^2 + H_3 (\theta - \theta_o)^3 + H_4 (\theta - \theta_o)^4 \right] \\
 & + \sum_{\phi} \left[V_1 (1 - \cos(\phi - \phi_o^0)) + V_2 (1 - \cos(2\phi - \phi_2^0)) + V_3 (1 - \cos(3\phi - \phi_3^0)) \right] + \sum_{\chi} K_{\chi} \chi^2 \\
 & + \sum_{b,b'} F_{bb'} (b - b_o)(b' - b'_o) + \sum_{\theta,\theta'} F_{\theta,\theta'} (\theta - \theta_o)(\theta' - \theta'_o) + \sum_{b,\theta} F_{b,\theta} (b - b_o)(\theta - \theta_o) \\
 & + \sum_{b,\phi} (b - b_o) [V_1 \cos \phi + V_2 \cos 2\phi + V_3 \cos 3\phi] + \sum_{b',\phi} (b' - b'_o) [V_1 \cos \phi + V_2 \cos 2\phi + V_3 \cos 3\phi] \\
 & + \sum_{\theta,\phi} (\theta - \theta_o) [V_1 \cos \phi + V_2 \cos 2\phi + V_3 \cos 3\phi] + \sum_{\theta,\theta',\phi} K_{\theta,\theta',\phi} \cos \phi (\theta' - \theta'_o)(\theta - \theta_o) \\
 & + \sum_{i,j} \frac{q_i q_j}{\epsilon r_{ij}} + \sum_{i,j} \left[\left(\frac{A_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^9 - \left(\frac{B_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Here, the first four terms are bond stretching, bending, torsion, and out-of-plane potentials, known as the valence term. The next seven terms are the cross terms describing the interactions between each valence term, and the last two terms are the non-bonded coulomb and van der Waals potentials. In calculating the non-bonded potentials, the atom-based summation with a cutoff radius of 9.5Å was used in the van der Waals summation with long range correction. Electrostatic interaction is treated using the distance-dependent dielectric constant method with the dielectric value of 2.5 r_{ij} was adopted [8].

Calculation of elastic modulus

The mechanical properties are calculated using the Parrinello-Rahman fluctuation method[9] where uniform external stress is applied to the unit-cell and the deviations of the resultant strain values at each simulation step are monitored. In this simulation, external stress equivalent to the atmospheric pressure, 1atm, is applied to the normal directions in all planes of the unit-cell. All the components of the stiffness matrix can be

obtained from the fluctuation formulation given below. During the $N\sigma T$ (constant stress) ensemble, the ensemble average of the strain perturbations are determined from the deformation tensor and the metric tensor, and the stiffness matrix of the unit cell can be calculated as shown below

$$C_{ijkl} = \frac{k_B T}{\langle V \rangle} \langle \delta \varepsilon_{ij} \delta \varepsilon_{kl} \rangle^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where k_B is Boltzman`s constant, T is the temperature during the ensemble and $\langle V \rangle$ is the ensemble average of the cell volume.

Calculation of CTE

The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) is estimated from volume or density-temperature relation obtained from a cooling down or heating up simulation where the pressure keeps up with constant value, 1 atm. The thermal characteristics of polymer are sensitive to the temperature, thus, the temperature change had better have small range. The coefficient of volume thermal expansion, α , is defined as

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{V} \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial T} \right)_P = -\frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} \right)_P \quad (3)$$

where V , T , ρ and P are the volume, temperature, density and pressure of the unit cell. For isotropic materials, the coefficient of volume thermal expansion is closely approximated as three times the coefficient of linear thermal expansion, β . The two CTEs have the relation, $\alpha \approx 3\beta$.

Molecular Dynamics Procedures

The unit cells for the MD simulation were constructed as amorphous periodic cells where the alumina particle was embedded at the center of the unit cell. After that, the potential energy of the cells was minimized using conjugation gradient method. To establish equilibrium state, the isothermal(NVT) ensemble simulation is performed for 200ps with 1fs time step at 300 K. Then, isothermal-isobaric(NPT) ensemble simulation was performed at 500 K which is higher than the glass transition temperature(T_g) of epoxy and 1 atm to make cells fully amorphous state. Then the temperature was decreased below T_g and the isobaric ensemble was applied to equilibrate the cells at room temperature 300 K.

The elastic moduli were obtained from the constant stress ensemble($N\sigma T$) simulation combined with the fluctuation scheme. The CTE and T_g were obtained from the cooling down simulation using isobaric ensemble(NPT) at 1 atm. The cooling down rate is 20K/500ps from 340 K to 280 K. The rate is slow enough to have equilibrated density at each temperature.

MD Simulation Results

As the MD simulation result have a large fluctuation generally, the value is obtained from averaged result of the five different simulations in each case. The averaging values and deviations are arranged in Table 2. Because the cases 1, 3, 6 and 7 have larger standard deviations(STD) than the other cases, five more simulations are performed to improve the statistical accuracy. The results show an enhanced reinforcing effect as the

particle size decreases. The nanocomposites including the smallest particles have the largest value, and the value of the nanosomposites is 80% higher than that of the pure epoxy.

For estimating the CTE values, only four cases, case 2, 3, 6 and 7, are used. Each case is simulated two times and the CTE of the pure epoxy and nanocomposites obtained from present MD simulations are listed in Table 2. Compared with the CTE of pure epoxy, CTE of the nanocomposites structures are lowered and it decreases as the particle radius decreases. But each case is simulated only two times and the number of simulation times is not enough statistically to estimate the CTE. To describe the particle size effect in the CTE at different particle radius, more MD simulations are need to obtained the CTE of the nanocomposites.

Table 2 The elastic moduli and CTEs of MD simulation

CASE	E (5 results)		E (10 results)		G (5 results)		G (10 results)		CTE (2 results)	
	AVG [GPa]	STD [GPa]	AVG [GPa]	STD [GPa]	AVG [GPa]	STD [GPa]	AVG [GPa]	STD [GPa]	AVG [10 ⁻⁴ /°C]	STD [10 ⁻⁴ /°C]
1	5.87	0.812	6.22	0.715	2.18	0.335	2.32	0.304	-	-
2	5.68	0.227	-	-	2.1	0.099	-	-	0.959	0.250
3	5.61	0.857	5.14	0.834	2.11	0.359	1.91	0.347	1.141	0.047
4	4.77	0.365	-	-	1.76	0.147	-	-	-	-
5	4.50	0.373	-	-	1.66	0.172	-	-	-	-
6	4.51	0.582	4.42	0.459	1.66	0.235	1.64	0.186	1.012	0.050
7	4.14	0.648	4.00	0.527	1.52	0.250	1.47	0.207	1.143	0.181
Epoxy	3.36				1.222				1.689	0.160

MULTISCALE BRIDGING METHOD

Effective interface model

In order to describe the particle size effect of the nanocomposites in continuum-based analysis, multi-inclusion model[10] was adopted and the effective interface between the particle and the matrix was considered as an extra phase to describe the particle size effect[4]. In multi-inclusion model, it is assumed that N phases are embedded into the infinite medium with an unknown fourth order stiffness tensor, C_{inf} . The applicability of the multi-inclusion model to the functionally graded materials (FGM) was successfully investigated [12] and the continuum modeling of the nanocomposites with effective interface can be regarded as a special case of FGMs having uniform material properties in interface. Thus, the overall domain of the nanocomposites is defined as three-phase structure consists of the particle, interface, and the matrix. In the derivation of the effective thermoelastic properties, field decomposition into two parts, loading field and residual field, is a convenient way to obtain the closed form solutions of the effective elastic modulus and CTE. Constitutive equations of the composites in terms of the effective elastic and thermal modulus can be given as

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = \mathbf{C}^* \langle \varepsilon \rangle + \lambda^* \theta \quad (4)$$

$$\langle \varepsilon \rangle = \mathbf{D}^* \langle \sigma \rangle + \alpha^* \theta \quad (5)$$

where, \mathbf{C}^* and \mathbf{D}^* are the effective elastic stiffness and compliance matrix and λ^* and α^* are the thermal stress and strain tensor of the composites, and θ is temperature change. The bracket $\langle \cdot \rangle = \frac{1}{V} \int_V (\cdot) dV$ indicates the volume average of the local fields.

Effective elastic modulus

For the effective elastic modulus, only loading field under the external displacement are needed and the equivalent inclusion method(EIM) can generate following consistent equation,

$$\mathbf{C}_r (\varepsilon^\infty + \varepsilon_r^d) = \mathbf{C}_{\text{inf}} (\varepsilon^\infty + \varepsilon_r^d - \varepsilon_r^*) \quad (6)$$

where, ε^∞ is the applied strain at the boundary of the infinite medium, ε_r^d and ε_r^* are the perturbed strain and eigenstrain of the r^{th} phase respectively and the fourth order tensor \mathbf{C}_r and \mathbf{C}_{inf} are the stiffness matrix of r^{th} phase and infinite medium respectively. After some manipulations of Eq.(6) with respect to the eigenstrain field with the average strain and stress scheme, average quantity of the loading field(superscript I) over the entire domain of the composites can be obtained as follows

$$\langle \varepsilon^I \rangle_R = \varepsilon^\infty + \langle \varepsilon^d \rangle_R = (\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{S}\Phi) \varepsilon^\infty \quad (7)$$

$$\langle \sigma^I \rangle_R = \sigma^\infty + \langle \sigma^d \rangle_R = [\mathbf{I} + (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I})\Phi] \varepsilon^\infty \quad (8)$$

where,

$$\Phi = \sum_{r=1}^N f_r \Phi_r = \sum_r f_r [(\mathbf{C}_{\text{inf}} - \mathbf{C}_r)^{-1} \mathbf{C}_{\text{inf}} - \mathbf{S}]^{-1} \quad (9)$$

and \mathbf{S} is the Eshelby's tensor[13] of a spherical inclusion. Then, from Eq.(7) and Eq.(9), effective elastic modulus can be given as

$$\mathbf{C}^* = \mathbf{C}_{\text{inf}} \left[\mathbf{I} + (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I}) \left(\sum_{r=1}^N f_r \Phi_r \right) \right] \left[\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{S} \left(\sum_{r=1}^N f_r \Phi_r \right) \right]^{-1}. \quad (10)$$

In order to use Eq.(10) to obtain the effective elastic modulus of the nanocomposites, elastic modulus and the volume fraction of the effective interface should be obtained. The volume fraction of the effective interface was obtained from the radial density distribution of the matrix polymer and elastic modulus can be implicitly obtained from the following equation.

$$\mathbf{C}_i = \mathbf{C}^* \left[\mathbf{I} - \left\{ f_i \left(\mathbf{I} + (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I})(f_p \Phi_p + f_m \Phi_m) - \mathbf{C}^* \mathbf{C}_{\text{inf}}^{-1} \left(\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{S}(f_p \Phi_p + f_m \Phi_m) \right) \right)^{-1} + \mathbf{S} \right\}^{-1} \right] \quad (11)$$

In this study, \mathbf{C}_{inf} is set equal to the stiffness matrix of the composites \mathbf{C}^* . Thus, the solution of the Eq.(10) is numerically solved(This is similar to the Self Consistent method). On the other hands, in the bridging process using Eq.(11), the effective stiffness matrix of the nannocomposites is already given and \mathbf{C}_i was obtained under the assumption that the stiffness matrix of the infinite medium \mathbf{C}_{inf} is equal to the stiffness matrix of the nanocomposites obtained from MD simulation.

Effective coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE)

Similar to the effective elastic modulus, effective thermal modulus can be derived from the equivalent inclusion method of the residual field. In case of the residual field problem of composites, due to the mismatch of the CTE of the particle and matrix, particle can be regarded as an inhomogeneous inhomogeneity and the consistent equation for the equivalent inclusion can be given as

$$\mathbf{C}_r (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^\infty + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r^d - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r^T) = \mathbf{C}_{\text{inf}} (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^\infty + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r^d - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r^T - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r^{**}) = \mathbf{C}_{\text{inf}} (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^\infty + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r^d - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r^*) \quad (12)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r^d = \mathbf{S} (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r^T + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r^{**}) = \mathbf{S} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_r^*. \quad (13)$$

In case of residual field, the derivation of the effective thermal stress or strain tensor can be obtained from the fixed boundary condition that the average strain in the composites caused by the temperature variation is zero. Average stress of the residual field (superscript II) is given as

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{II} \rangle_R = \mathbf{C}_{\text{inf}} (\mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\Phi} \mathbf{S})^{-1} \sum_r^N f_r [\boldsymbol{\Phi}_r (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I}) + \mathbf{I}] \mathbf{C}_r^{-1} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_r \theta = \boldsymbol{\lambda}^* \theta. \quad (14)$$

Then, the effective thermal stress tensor of the nanocomposites is obtained as

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda}^* = \mathbf{C}_{\text{inf}} (\mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\Phi} \mathbf{S})^{-1} \sum_{r=1}^N f_r [\boldsymbol{\Phi}_r (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I}) + \mathbf{I}] \mathbf{C}_r^{-1} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_r. \quad (15)$$

As can be seen in Eq.(15), effective thermal stress tensor is directly coupled to the stiffness matrix of each phases. Thus, the determination of the elastic modulus of the effective interface is prior to the thermal stress tensor. Similar to the derivation of the elastic modulus, Eq.(15) can be rearranged with respect to the thermal stress tensor of the interface given as

$$\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i = f_i^{-1} \mathbf{C}_i [\boldsymbol{\Phi}_i (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I}) + \mathbf{I}]^{-1} \left\{ (\mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\Phi} \mathbf{S}) \mathbf{C}_{\text{inf}}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\lambda}^* - f_p [\boldsymbol{\Phi}_p (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I}) + \mathbf{I}] \mathbf{C}_p^{-1} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_p - f_m [\boldsymbol{\Phi}_m (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I}) + \mathbf{I}] \mathbf{C}_m^{-1} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_m \right\} \quad (16)$$

and the CTE of the effective interface can be obtained from following relation.

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_i = -\mathbf{D}_i \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i \quad (17)$$

Where, \mathbf{D}_i is the elastic compliance tensor of the effective interface and the effective CTE of the nanocomposites can be obtained from

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}^* = -\mathbf{D}^* \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*. \quad (18)$$

BRIDGING ANALYSIS RESULTS

Elastic modulus

Radial density distribution of the nanocomposites is shown in Figure 2 and there exists a highly concentrated adsorption layer showing much higher density than the pure polyimide. Thus, the adsorption layer can be regarded as a different phase from the matrix itself. Defining the outer thickness of the interface $t_{\text{adsorption}}$ as 4\AA , the thickness of the interface can be obtained from the relation given below.

$$r_{\text{matrix}} = r_{\text{peak}} + t_{\text{adsorption}} \quad (19)$$

$$t_{\text{interface}} = r_{\text{matrix}} - r_{\text{particle}} \quad (20)$$

The thickness of the interface is listed in Table 3 and it was set to 7\AA for simplicity. Then the elastic modulus of the interface was obtained from Eq.(11) and arranged in Table 3. As the particle radius increases, due to the particle size effect, the elastic modulus of the interface asymptotically decreases. In order to describe such variations, the elastic modulus of the interface was fitted into exponential function of the particle radius r_p as $E_{int} = 3.36 + 96 \exp(-0.426r_p)$ and $G_{int} = 1.22 + 33 \exp(-0.41r_p)$. Assuming that the interface is isotropic, the stiffness matrix of the interface can be obtained from the Young's and shear modulus of the interface, as $C_i = C_i(r_p)$.

Figure 2 Radial density distribution of the nanocomposites obtained from molecular model and the definition of the effective interface.

Table 3 Thickness, elastic modulus and CTE of the effective interface.

No. of epoxy unit	$r_{particle}$ (Å)	r_{peak} (Å)	$t_{interface}$ (Å)	E_{int} (GPa)	G_{int} (GPa)	CTE($10^{-5}/K$)
9	6.0	8.65	6.68	8.20	3.09	-
15	7.0	9.85	6.85	8.82	3.28	2.47
21	7.9	10.25	6.35	8.16	3.15	4.14
24	8.2	11.05	6.85	6.83	2.57	-
27	8.6	11.35	6.75	5.94	2.24	-
30	8.9	11.75	6.85	6.04	2.23	-
42	10.0	12.45	6.45	4.19	1.57	-

Figure 3 depicts the elastic modulus of the nanocomposites obtained from the present bridging method and the MD simulations. As the radius of the reinforcing filler increases, the present bridging model favorably reflects the particle size effect obtained from the MD simulations and gradually decreases to the Mori-Tanaka estimations where the elastic modulus of the interface becomes that of the epoxy matrix. Using the present bridging method, elastic modulus of the nanocomposites at various particle radius and volume fractions are efficiently extrapolated in Figure 4.

CTE of the interface corresponds to the particle radius of the 7.0 and 7.9 Å were obtained from Eqs(16,17) and arranged in Table 3. Similar to the elastic modulus, CTE of the interface was fitted using an exponential function of the particle radius as $CTE_{int} = 17 - 37 \exp(-0.13r_p)$ with a unit of $10^{-5}/K$. Figure 5 depicts the CTE of the nanocomposites obtained from present bridging method and MD simulations. As the particle size increases, CTE of the nanocomposites asymptotically increases. Comparing

the MD simulation results, CTE of the nanocomposites at the fitting points exactly reproduce the MD simulation results. For more accurate estimation of the particle size effect on the CTE of the nanocomposites at various particle sizes, more MD simulation results at various particle sizes are needed.

Figure 3 Elastic modulus of the nanocomposites obtained from the present multiscale bridging method and the molecular dynamics simulations.

Figure 4 Elastic modulus of the nanocomposites at various volume fractions and particle radii.

Figure 5 CTE of the nanocomposites obtained from the present bridging method

CONCLUSION

In this study, a sequential multi-scale bridging method was suggested to construct efficient micromechanics model to predict the thermoelastic properties of alumina/epoxy nanocomposites. In order to consider the size effect of nanocomposites, molecular dynamics simulation was implemented to obtain the nano-scale physical and chemical information. As a result of MD simulations, it has been found that the reinforcing effect of the particle critically depends on the size of the reinforcing filler. Both the Young's modulus and the shear modulus of the nanocomposites decreased as the particle radius increases. CTE of the nanocomposites also showed similar tendency and smaller particle reinforced cases showed lowered thermal expansion characteristics. Based on the MD simulation results, efficient scale bridging method for the thermoelastic properties of the nanocomposites were developed based on the multi-inclusion model. In all numerical simulations results, the size effect of the nanoparticle on the thermoelastic modulus was efficiently described.

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